

EXTRUSION DEPOSITION OF CARBON NANOTUBES (CNT)/POLY ETHER ETHER KETONE (PEEK)

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the properties of PEEK/CNT composite filaments fabricated through extrusion deposition, as a first step into understanding the parameters required for layer-by-layer material deposition. The extrusion deposition is part of the additive manufacturing techniques, able to manufacture thermoplastic composites with a high degree of freedom. The results showed that the temperature does not affect significantly the tensile strength of the composite, where the pure PEEK filament seems to decrease in strength with an increase of processing temperature. For the specimens tested the 1% and 5% CNT loadings into PEEK matrix did not give a reinforcing effect.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper presents an investigation into the use of net-shaped reinforced PEEK additive manufacturing technologies. The material extrusion technology, known also as fused deposition modelling (FDM) was chosen as the prime technology due to its relative robustness and ease of modification when compared to equally mature technologies such as Laser Sintering of polymers. Unlike Laser Sintering, which requires expensive CO₂ laser based optics, and high-speed scanners, the material extrusion technology is more basic. Systems can be manufactured and scaled up in size with ease, and the raw material consumption is more closely linked with the single part manufacture, unlike Laser Sintering where batch manufacturing is the more economic method of usage.

The majority of polymers used in material deposition are low Tg polymers such as Polylactic Acid (PLA); Polycarbonate (PC); Polyamide (PA) or Acrylonitrile Butadiene (ABS). In the high temperature range, there are currently only two materials available, both optimized for use only in combination with the Stratasys extrusion system: Poly Ether Imide (PEI), known under the trade name ULTEM 1010 and 9085 and Poly Phenyl Sulfone (PPSF).

PEEK is being widely marketed as a polymer capable of replacing metal in many applications. It has been recently introduced as a material available for powder fusion processes [1, 2] but no developments had been published for the extrusion deposition processes. The recyclable polymer has a melting temperature of 343°C and possesses exceptional mechanical properties with resistance to chemicals, wear, fatigue and creep even at high operating temperatures where it is commonly used in service. With a density of 1.3g/cm³ it is below half that of Aluminium [2.7g/cm³]. With the addition of

glass or carbon fibres as structural reinforcement, PEEK compounds have high strength and modulus values similar to Aluminium, but with a much lower density, which results in an excellent strength to weight ratio and in some applications can offer up to a 70% weight reduction for the equivalent mechanical strength and stiffness [3].

This study is examining for the first time; PEEK and CNT reinforced PEEK deposition, focusing on the properties of the deposited filament as the first step into the investigation. Understanding the filament microstructure in relation to process parameters is critical for fabrication of robust and reliable structures. Similarly, a close examination into the surface of the filament can provide useful insights into the layer-to-layer bonding, an intrinsic weakness of the additive manufacturing processes. The importance of filament investigations had been shown before in a few other studies: ABS monofilament feedstock and in-plane mesostructures [4], carbon fibre filled ABS [5], and short glass fibre reinforced ABS filament [6].

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Extrusion system

A MendleMax v2.0 from Maker's Tool Works was chosen as the base framework due to it's predominately Aluminium construction and simplistic Cartesian design, allowing for additional modifications. The extrusion heads are interchangeable and a number of designs are commercially available. An E3D online V6 all metal hot-end was selected with a number of interchangeable brass extrusion tips of varying diameter. This design features an Aluminium heater block and heat sink as shown in Fig. 1, with stainless steel centre tubing and no PEEK or PTFE internal liner, which restricts high temperature processing. An additional heated build base was designed in Aluminium capable of much higher temperatures than the standard MendleMax design.

Figure 1: E3D online V6 hot-end (Image courtesy of E3D)

2.2 Materials

PEEK 450G supplied by Victrex was extrusion compounded with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in 1 % and 5% loadings. The handling of loose CNTs was avoided by using a pre-prepared commercial product, Plasticyl PEEK 1001 by Nanocyl S.A.[7]. Plasticyl PEEK 1001 is a CNT/PEEK masterbatch incorporating 10% by weight, multi-wall CNTs.

2.3 Filament fabrication

Once a successful extrusion profile had been established for pure PEEK 450G, batches of total weight 500g of each blend were manually mixed prior to loading into the main feed hopper of the twin - screw extrusion compounder. It was not found to be necessary to alter the extrusion profile for the different blends. The filament produced had a diameter of 2.7 mm \pm 0.3. The prepared filament was dried in an industrial oven for 5hrs at 150°C prior to use.

<i>Die temp(°C)</i>	360
<i>Zone1-5 temp(°C)</i>	360
<i>Melt temp (°C)</i>	344
<i>Screw speed (rpm)</i>	90

Table 1: Extrusion profile for melt compounding

2.4 Extrusion deposition of composite filaments

The geometry shown in Fig. 2 was built in 0.2mm layers with a 0.8 mm diameter extrusion tip, which created a thin-wall structure of a single tool-path 10mm high. The samples were built with a fixed deposition speed of 30mm/s. The sample geometries were built at a range of temperatures: 350, 365, 380 and 390 °C, and all the samples were cooled to 150 °C before removal from the heated build base. The single wall samples were sectioned into approximately 0.2 x 0.8 x 90 mm test specimens by manually peeling the individual layers apart.

Figure 2: (a) Thin-wall geometry selected for extrusion deposition (b) peeling of the composite filament for tensile testing

2.4 Tensile testing of filaments

The individual filament ends were mounted on a card to protect the sample ends from breaking at the jaw. The filaments with the protected ends were inserted in the serrated jaws of the Lloyd Instruments EZ20 mechanical testing machine. The samples were tested at a speed of 5 mm x minute⁻¹ to an extension of 10 mm using a 500N load cell according to the ASTM D 3379-75[8]. Between 10 and 15 samples were tested for each temperature and type of sample.

2.5 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Microstructure and the fracture surface of the deposited filament were carried out by scanning electron microscopy SEM (Hitachi S-3200N, Japan). The secondary electron images were taken under 25 KV acceleration voltages.

2.6 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Thermal analysis measurements on plain PEEK filament and PEEK/5% CNT samples were carried out in a Mettler Toledo DSC-821. All samples were heated from room temperature to 400 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere at 10 °C x min⁻¹ heating rate and cooled at the same rate from 400 °C to room temperature. The tests were repeated three times on each sample and the average results of the three repeats were reported.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure analysis

The Fig. 3 presents the fracture surface of the pure PEEK and PEEK/CNT filaments. It is believed that the fibrous morphology noticed across the composite filament structures represent the CNTs. For comparison the fracture surfaces of the PEEK filaments were examined but no fibrous, “spiky” structure was noticed.

Figure 3: (a) (b) Fracture surface of PEEK/5%CNT filament (c) (d) Fracture surface of PEEK

The surface of the filaments was also examined. Fig 4 shows the surface of PEEK and PEEK/5% CNT filaments. Both types of samples experience two types of surfaces: (1) smooth; uniform and (2) uneven, porous structure with cavities ranging from 10µm to 30µm diameter. The source of these cavities is unclear at this stage. It is possible that they are the result of moisture trapped within compounded composite rod/wire as the PEEK matrix has not been dried prior to CNT compounding. The compounded rod was dried prior to extrusion deposition process.

Figure 4: (a) Surfaces of pure PEEK filaments (b) surfaces of PEEK/5% CNT filaments

3.2 Tensile testing

The tensile strength values of pure PEEK filaments and PEEK/CNT composite filaments with 1% and 5% loadings deposited at various temperatures are shown in Table 1. As it can be seen, the tensile strength of pure PEEK filaments seems to be influenced by the deposition temperature. A higher temperature leads to a lower tensile strength. For composite filament of 1% and 5% loadings, the differences induced by the deposition temperature seems to disappear. This could be due to the higher thermal conductivity induced by the presence of CNTs, which leads to less temperature variations amongst the built structures and subsequently between filaments and a better, more homogenous cooling profile. Previous studies [9] reported an 18% increase in thermal conductivity of PA powder incorporating CNTs in comparison with the pure thermoplastic powder.

Deposition Temperature [°C]	Tensile Strength (MPa)		
	PEEK	PEEK/1%CNT	PEEK/5%CNT
350	81.1 ± 6.3	61.4 ± 13.3	87.4 ± 11.6
365	68.0 ± 11.4	87.7 ± 7.0	80.3 ± 12.4
380	68.0 ± 10.5	80.3 ± 7.3	82.5 ± 4.6
390	56.8 ± 11.1	-	-

Table 2: Filament tensile strength of PEEK/CNT composites at 1% and 5% loadings

The results in Table 2 show also a relatively high standard deviation, which highlights a significant variation between filaments within the same built structure. One possible reason responsible for these variations could be related with the dimensional accuracy of the deposited filament. An uneven, non-uniform filament could lead to significant errors in diameter measurements. Another cause of these variations could be associated with the composition of the filament. The CNT reinforcement was added as PEEK masterbatch with 10% by weight CNT concentration, but the grade of PEEK used in the masterbatch it is not specified by the supplier. For the PEEK filament incorporating 5%CNT, the

amount of unknown grade of PEEK is reasonably high and could influence significantly the mechanical performance of the parts produced. Depending on the molecular weight, two grades of PEEK can have different tensile strength and elongation. For example, PEEK150/151G grade has a 105MPa tensile strength and 30% elongation at break [10], where PEEK 450G grade has 98MPa tensile strength and 45% elongation at break [11]. PEEK 150/151G and PEEK 450G are grades supplied by Victrex Plc. The quality of the CNT dispersion within the filament is not known either and it is likely that the CNT agglomerations are still present within the structure. The SEM micrographs of as received Nanocyl™ NC 7000 nanotube powders presented by Alig et al, [12], showed a “combed yarn” structure with larger agglomerates.

Fig 5 presents the stress-strain curve of PEEK/CNT composites at 1% and 5% loadings by comparison with plain PEEK filament, all fabricated at the same temperature 380°C. The results show a higher strength and modulus in the composite filaments in comparison to the plain PEEK filament. The percentage strain was reduced in the composite filaments with 5% CNT loadings, indicating the sample is becoming more brittle and less tough. It is unclear at this stage whether the CNTs have a reinforcement effect or simply act as a good heat absorber, creating a more homogenous and better crystalline composite structure. The effect of temperature is observed also in Fig 6, when comparing plain PEEK 450G filaments at two different temperatures: 365 °C and 390 °C.

Figure 5: Stress-Strain curves of PEEK/CNT composite filaments with 1% and 5% loadings at 380°C

Figure 6: Stress- Strain curves of PEEK 450G filaments extruded at 365 and 390°C

Fig. 6 presents the stress-strain curves of plain PEEK 450G filaments fabricated at different operating temperatures. It is interesting to notice that the filament deposited at lower temperatures 365°C has a higher strength and modulus.

3.2 Thermo analysis results

The DSC analysis was employed to help us understand further the effect of temperature and CNTs incorporation on the fabricated filament. Table 3 presents the crystallinity values as well as the melting and crystallization temperatures for plain PEEK 450G at two different temperatures (365 °C and 390 °C) and PEEK/5%CNT extruded at 365 °C. Fig 7 presents also the DSC traces for the three types of filament. As previously noticed in other studies [9, 13], the presence of CNTs shift the melting and crystallization temperatures to higher values. During cooling, the CNTs act as a nucleating agent, activating the crystallization and moving the crystallization temperature to higher temperatures, in our case by approximately 13 °C. However, there are a few studies, which noticed a decrease in crystallization and the effect was explained by a reduction in the polymer chain mobility [14] or in some cases by the presence of PEI or PES polymers used as compatibilisers [15]. It is important to mention that the composites tested here originated from a PEEK 450G compounded with an unknown PEEK/CNT masterbatch grade, which could have a contribution towards the obtained DSC values. However, in spite of this behaviour, the crystallinity seems to remain unaffected.

	PEEK 365 °C	PEEK 390 °C	PEEK/5%CNT 365 °C
<i>Crystallinity [%]</i>	28.6 ± 0.6	27.5 ± 1.9	29.1 ± 0.4
<i>Melting Temp [°C]</i>	339 ± 0.4	341.0 ± 0.3	345.7 ± 1.2
<i>Crystallization Temp [°C]</i>	290.6 ± 0.05	290.9 ± 0.5	303.7 ± 0.1

Table 3: DSC values for plain PEEK 450G and PEEK/CNT composite filaments

Figure 7: DSC traces of plain PEEK 450G and PEEK/5% CNT filaments showing (a) effect of CNT incorporation and (b) effect of temperature

The plain PEEK filament extruded at different temperatures was also examined and compared in Table 3 and Fig 7(b). A slight increase in melting temperature was noticed in the PEEK filament fabricated at 390 °C, as a result of a different extruding temperature and therefore slightly different cooling profile, but the crystallisation temperature and crystallinity remained the same as the filament fabricated at 365 °C. It is difficult to comment at this stage whether this difference in crystallinity is the main reason for the differences in mechanical performance noticed between the two plain PEEK filaments presented in Fig. 6. It has been shown that PEEK has interesting and complicated crystal structures, some still debated in the literature [16, 17], and therefore could influence the strength and modulus of the extruded filaments.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Although the CNTs were added to improve the strength and reinforce the plain polymer, their presence seems to influence more the processing behaviour rather than the reinforcing performance. At the 1% and 5% loadings, the temperature processing window was increased from 350-365°C to 350-380°C, making the extrusion deposition process less sensitive to other parameters (e.g. speed of deposition or environment temperature) and therefore providing a more robust system. The study highlights the complexity of the material combined with what it looks at a first glance a simple material extrusion process. Quality of the CNT dispersion with the matrix, robustness and control of the deposition process and quality of the fabricated filament as well as the lack of temperature control above the deposition plate have an important role in the fabrication of components.

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